

DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE CONDUCTIVE FABRIC BY COPPER METAL COATING APPROACH FOR E-TEXTILE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This work aims to manufacture the conductive fabric through the copper metal coating approach and to investigate the effect of fabric type on the conductivity of the selected types. We also explored increased in weight, and increased in thickness on the coated samples as well as effect of washing cycles and abrasion on the electrical conductivity of the samples. The electroless plating was chosen to fulfil this aim since the process allows the coating of non-conductive textile materials and it is relatively cheaper compared to other available options. We selected two different fabrics (polyamide and knitted cotton) to conduct the study.

Having coated structures with copper, we performed such tests including abrasion, weight increased percentage, thickness, washing cycles, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDX). The results revealed that while knitted cotton fabric showed conductive properties, polyamide fabric was non-conductive because of its dense and hydrophobic structure properties, thus the knitted cotton fabric can be considered suitable candidate for e-Textile applications.

Keywords

Cotton fabric, Elastomeric Polyamide, Conductivity, SEM, Electroless plating

1. Introduction

Wearable electronic systems are receiving significant attention recently because of the usage in human body motion monitoring¹, medical diagnosis², training in sports³ or other entertainment purposes so that the investment in this area is increasing. Wearable electronics is also an improving area for future clothing. As technology is growing that fast, new devices and numerous functions for textile products are inevitable. The various functions that expected from these textile products are provided in the concept of such devices as a display, sensors, and batteries etc., which all have a different working mechanisms and functions in or on the human body. Following this statement, electronic textile products are highly suitable for practical use with respect to their inherent properties as providing comfort, having warmth, lightness, and flexibility. Electronic textiles jumps on the other stage in fibre-based platforms or body-attachable types to promote industrializing important materials with an integrated format⁴.

Structural and physical properties of the fabrics called flexibility, breathability, absorption have an essential effect to develop such systems⁵. The advantage of the textile materials are providing comfort and mobility to the user with this respect textile based platforms do not limit the wearer. Therefore, the investments and research in that area are dramatically increased in the last decade to produce and improve wearable electronic platforms which are also called electronic textiles⁶. Application areas of e-textiles greatly affect the number and type of the e-textiles components within the structure. Although, to accomplish the task of the e-textile product, it is necessary to have a special groups of components such as sensors/electrodes, power supply, a communication network within the platform or/and having it as an external platform, an actuator and a data processor which all can be the basic elements of an e-textile product⁷. The electrical conductivity is the key property in order to manufacture such components. Generally, conductive properties are formed by metal strands woven into the construction of the textile or metal coating over the knitted, woven or nonwoven textile substrate. Conductive fibers consist of a non-conductive or less conductive substrate, which is then either coated or embedded with electrically conductive elements, often carbon, nickel, copper, gold, silver, titanium or PEDOT⁸⁻⁹. There are mainly three depositing ways for making

the fabric conductive, they can be deposited chemically by electroplating, sputtering or electroless plating. In this work, electroless plating was carried out to form a conductive fabric

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The fabric used in this work were elastomeric polyamide fabric (GSM= 252 g/m²) cotton knitted fabric (White Jersey single layer Knitted fabric, GSM= 198 g/m², Ne 23/1) and All reagents used were of analytical grade in this work.

For the sensitization: Tin (II) chloride (SnCl₂) anhydrous was acquired from Merck KGaA (Germany) and HCl solution was acquired from Riedel-de haen sigma Aldrich.

For the activation: AgNO₃ was purchased from Merck and Ammonia solution (25%) was acquired from Merck KGaA (Germany).

For plating purpose: Copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate was purchased from carlo erba reagents (France), potassium sodium tartrate (KNaC₄H₄O₆·4H₂O) and formaldehyde (HCHO) was acquired from Merck, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was acquired from Riedel-de haen sigma Aldrich⁸⁻⁹.

2.2. Procedures

There are different ways to make the fabric conductive e.g electroplating, sputtering, electroless plating process. For this work, we have selected the electroless plating process. The electroless plating was chosen to fulfil this aim since the process allows the coating of non-conductive textile materials and it is relatively cheaper compared to other available options.

Electroless plating is used to deposit a coating of a metal on a substrate without using an external power source, such as electricity. Unlike electroplating, usage of direct electric current is not required. Conventional electroless plating involves several heated pre-treatment and activation baths followed by one or more plating bath and then rinsing bath¹⁰⁻¹¹.

The process does not require any extra machines or electrical power source, it is purely a chemical reaction process. To carry out the procedure, firstly the fabric must be cleaned properly, with chemical cleanser to remove oil and other corrosive elements which sticks to the surface. The next steps follow to immerse the fabric in the plating solution. An oxidation-reduction process starts by the coating, metals deposit at the surface of the fabric, it adheres, and a layer of coating is thus formed¹².

This process is much less complex process compared with electroplating. Electro-less plating gives the user much more control over the process.

2.3. Analytical Methods

Electroless plating method was selected for this work. For making the fabric conductive, first of all, we washed the fabric with 5% non-ionic detergent at 30°C for 20 minutes in order to remove the oil, dust or impurities from the surface of the fabrics.

There are some steps that has been carried out for this work, which are sensitization, activation and plating process.

There were a lot of recipes in the literature and we selected the following recipe among them that was found to fit our requirements. After washing the samples, samples were rinsed with distilled water for about 5 minutes. Next step is sensitization. In the sensitization, we used Tin (II) chloride (SnCl₂) 5g/l, HCl (37%) solution 5ml/l at 25°C for 10 minutes. After the sensitization process, next step is activation. The purpose of activation process is to activate the fabrics for further plating process. Without proper activation process, we cannot achieve the required goals of copper coating on the fabric surface. In the activation process, we used AgNO₃ 10g/l and Ammonia solution (25%) 10ml/l at 25°C for 20 minutes. After activation,

fabrics were rinsed with distilled water. the next and important step is plating process. Plating bath consists of Copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate 10g/l, potassium sodium tartrate ($\text{KNaC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) 45g/l (Complexing agents), formaldehyde (HCHO) 20ml/l, and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 10g/l at 30°C for 20 minutes. Complexing agents minimize the formation of copper to copper hydroxides ($\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$)¹³.

After completing these treatment process, next step was the post treatment process. Plated fabric samples were rinsed with distilled water at 40°C for 20 minutes and dried in oven at 60°C . In electroless process, the reaction is catalysed by employing a suitable reducing agent which supplies the electron for reduction reaction and metal is deposited over the substrate¹⁴⁻¹⁵. The reactions can be shown as below.

Metal ion (M^+) + Reducing agent (Red) \rightarrow Metal Deposited + Oxidized product (Ox)

There are two reactions in electroless plating:

Here, M: Metal, e: electron, Red: Reducing agent, Ox: Oxidized product

Figure 1 below showing the schematic representation of electroless metal deposition and showing the Process flow of Conductive fabrics via Electroless Plating Process is given by figure 2. Low pressure Plasma treatment was also performed on the surface of the polyamide fabric to make it hydrophilic for electroless plating process¹⁶⁻¹⁷.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of electroless metal deposition

Figure 2: Process flow of Conductive fabrics via Electroless Plating Process

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Conductivity Analysis

All measurements of the conductivity of the fabric were carried out with digital multi meter device (Amprobe 15XP-B). The measurement of Cotton knitted fabrics' conductivity were made by logging the electrical resistance values (ohms).

3.2. Weight increased percentage

We performed the five samples of the polyamide fabric and the results are given below table. Weight increase percentage results gives information about how much weight gained after the coating process.

3.3. Thickness

Thickness test has been carried out with R&B Cloth thickness Tester (James Heal Instruments) with parameter 10g/cm^2 with 0.01mm accuracy. The standard used for measuring the thickness is D1777-96. The thickness values were taken from almost five different places on the fabric before and after the coating process and the average of these values was accepted as the thickness of the fabric. Thickness value showed that how much coating material deposited onto the surface of the fabrics. The results showed that the thickness values are uniform throughout the surface of the samples. Table I given below showing the results of weight increase percentage, conductivity and thickness of the samples.

Table I: Weight increase percentage, conductivity and thickness of the samples.

Samples	Weight increase %age		Resistance (Ω/cm)		Thickness (mm)	
	%age	StD	Ω	StD	mm	StD
Polyamide	1.168	0.954	-----	-----	0.6706	0.00391
Polyamide (plasma treated)	3.984	0.735	-----	-----	0.679	0.0099
Knitted Cotton	14.726	2.008	430	85.8	0.648	0.01924

Figure 3: Graphs of thickness and weight increased %age of Knitted cotton and polyamide

3.4. Abrasion Analysis

The abrasion test has been carried out in Martindale James H. Heal & Co. Ltd. The parameter set for polyamide fabric was 9KPa and the standard used for abrasion tests was D4966-12. This is the important test and abrasion tests used to measure a fabric's ability to withstand abrasion. The results showed that coated after 100 cycles of abrasion, knitted cotton fabric weight loss percentage is higher than elastomeric polyamide fabric. The reason is that the coated material deposited on cotton fabric is more than polyamide fabric and polyamide fabric was non-conductive, while knitted cotton fabric was conductive. The abrasion tests results are given below for polyamide, polyamide with plasma treated and knitted cotton fabrics in table II.

Table II: Abrasion Cycles of Polyamide and knitted fabric

Cycles	Polyamide		Polyamide (Plasma Treated)		Knitted Cotton			
	Weight loss		Weight loss		Weight loss		Resistance	
	(%)	StD	(%)	StD	(%)	StD	(Ω)	StD
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1298	390
10	--	--	--	--	2.406	0.63	2576	983
20	1.556	0.1799	0.38416	0.639	3.208	0.852	3920	1683
30	--	--	--	--	3.716	0.835	5956	2790
40	--	--	--	--	4.03	0.909	9240	4450
50	1.87	0.403	0.38298	0.621	4.304	0.972	11440	4612
60	--	--	--	--	4.556	0.967	15946	6346
70	--	--	--	--	4.762	0.959	22440	7949
80	--	--	--	--	4.98	1.004	28060	7419
90	--	--	--	--	5.138	1.069	36100	7133
100	2.052	0.391	0.3823	0.817	5.224	1.066	0	0

Figure 4: Graphs of Abrasion Cycles of Polyamide with and without plasma treated

Figure 5: Graphs of Abrasion Cycles of Knitted Cotton with Weight Loss % and resistance

3.5 Washing Cycles

We washed the fabric at 30°C for 20 minutes and dried at 60°C in Oven for 30 minutes and then we placed the sample at room temperature in the standard testing atmosphere 65±2%RH in order to make it complete dry. After the 24 hours, we checked it and measured the weight.

Table III: Washing Cycles of Polyamide and knitted fabric

Washing Cycles	Polyamide		Polyamide (Plasma Treated)		Knitted Cotton			
	Weight		Weight		Weight		Resistance	
	(g)	StD	(g)	StD	(g)	StD	(Ω)	StD
0	0.52946	0.00757	0.43628	0.00708	0.32204	0.00694	260.6	44.7
1	0.52654	0.00735	0.4327	0.00721	0.31614	0.0074	357.2	54.6
2	0.52518	0.00744	0.43098	0.00719	0.3104	0.00715	405	69.5
3	0.5239	0.00737	0.42992	0.00706	0.30736	0.00747	432	77.9
4	0.52276	0.00724	0.42934	0.00699	0.30448	0.00745	473.4	85.3
5	0.5223	0.00737	0.42898	0.00702	0.2836	0.0418	497.2	84.9

Figure 6: Graphs of Washing Cycles of Knitted Cotton, Polyamide with and without plasma treated

3.6. Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The scanning electron microscopy is used for surface topography and composition. TESCAN VEGA 3 has been used for SEM images. The view of coated/conductive and uncoated/non-conductive regions on the fabric was made by Scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Figure 7: SEM images of the a). Uncoated knitted cotton at 8.5Kx magnification, (b). Coated Knitted Cotton at 8.5Kx magnification (c). Uncoated polyamide at 5Kx magnification, (d). Coated polyamide at 5Kx magnification, (e). Uncoated Polyamide with plasma treated at 1Kx magnification, (f). Coated polyamide with plasma treated at 2.5Kx magnification

Figure 8: SEM images of the Coated-Knitted Cotton fabric at specific point showing the coated material onto the surface of the fabric with close view

3.7. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX)

EDX is an analytical technique used for the elemental analysis or chemical characterization of a sample. It has been carried out via scanning electron microscopy TESCAN VEGA 3. EDX results showed in the Figure 8, 9 and 10 showed that after the coating process, copper and silver are deposited onto the surface of the fabrics. In the cotton fabric, copper are more deposited (89%) and in polyamide fabric (53%) and in polyamide with plasma treated (72%).

Figure 9: EDX image of knitted cotton fabric

Figure 10: EDX image of Polyamide fabric

Figure 11: EDX image of Polyamide (with plasma treated) fabric

4. Conclusions

Knitted cotton fabric and the other Elastomeric Polyamide (Without plasma and with plasma treated) were used in this work. Among them, knitted cotton fabric showed the conductivity after the metal coating process. Although, we performed the electroless process on the polyamide fabric, it did not show the conductive properties. The possible reason for this result because of the structural properties polyamide fabric which is thick and dense. Thus electroless plating solution couldn't penetrate inside the structure of the polyamide surface that resulted in non-conductive areas within the structure. In addition to this, polyamide fabric shows the hydrophobic properties and water/solution couldn't penetrate into its pores properly. We also tried plasma treated polyamide fabric and results showed that plasma treated polyamide fabric absorbed more materials/solution as compared to non-treated polyamide. However, it also showed non-conductive behaviour because of the non-uniform coating on the surface of the polyamide fabric, thus we are proceeded with knitted cotton fabric that is the suitable candidate for different E-Textile Applications.

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